

But until now, a phytoalexin response in the genetically based, cultivar- and race-specific resistance of rice to blast has not been reported. We have found that inoculation with avirulent blast races produced momilactone phytoalexins in genetically resistant cultivars.

After wound inoculation, leaf extracts were subjected to thin-layer chromatography and directly bioassayed by spraying the plate with spores of the green fungus *Cladosporium cucumerinum* (see figure). The white zones correspond to areas of inhibition of *C. cucumerinum*, showing the presence of phytoalexins. Although uninoculated tissue contains low levels of inhibitory compounds, the incompatible reaction clearly results in enhanced phytoalexin production,

TW TP RW RP mA
Cladosporium bioassay of leaf extracts of Tetep (T) and IR36 (R) inoculated with *Pyricularia oryzae* (P) or water (W). Momilactone A standard (mA) was included.

Momilactone production in rice with blast disease.

Isolate	Momilactone production	
	Tetep	IR36
2017	- (S)	+ (R)
750778	+ (R)	- (S)

^a- indicates negligible momilactone production, + indicates momilactone production. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

including the momilactones.

Two cultivars, Tetep and IR36, were tested with the isolates 2017 and 750778 (see table). Phytoalexin production is correlated with race- and cultivar-specific resistance. (This work was supported by a Ministry of Overseas Development, U. K., grant.) ■

Varietal resistance to kernel smut

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Kernel smut was first observed in a mild form on the variety Kannagi at Sundaraperumal koil and Swamimalai areas in Thanjavur district during 1975 kuruvai. In 1976, almost all varieties were affected. In Thanjavur delta, disease incidence in the kuruvai crop is heavy when monsoon rains are early. In 1981, incidence was severe.

Screening of 20 short-duration varieties and prerelease cultures assessed disease resistance. Four observations of 25 panicles per variety were made at 3-day intervals from the initial appearance of disease symptoms. The highest disease incidence for the four counts is given in the table. ■

Varietal resistance to kernel smut in Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Parentage	Kernel smut (%) (mean of 25 panicles)
ADT31	IR8/Cult 340	10.9
ADT34	IR8/Rodjolele	6.5
TKM9	TKM7/IR8	5.7
ADT36	Triveni/IR20	10.1
ADT33	IR8/Cult 340	6.3
IR50	Nam Sagui 19/IR2071-88//IR2061-214-3-6-2	0.0
Kannagi	IR8/TKM6	9.6
IET4786	CR10-114/CR115	1.8
AD16773	Ratna/ADT33	43.4
AD14018	AUT31/IE3125	3.1
AD14226	ADT30/CO 39	2.6
AD15426	IR30/IR28	0.0
AD14185	Pusa 140/Ratna	13.2
AD16674	ADT31/AD11585	0.0
AD14758	Ratna/AD11585	0.0
AD9246	ADT31/AD198	7.5
AD13887	ADT31/IR36	0.0
AD16586	Tiruvani/IR20//TKM6/IET2222	0.0
Pusa 186-10-4-5	Pusa 140-51///Amir//Sona/improved Sabarmathi	0.0
CO 33	IR8/ADT27	8.4

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

An improved method for field screening cultures resistant to brown planthopper

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To field evaluate at different sites rice cultures resistant to brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, it has been necessary to develop methods to increase the BPH populations because populations are often too low or unevenly distributed. A modification of the method using resurgence-causing

insecticides is being successfully utilized at AICRIP (Hyderabad) and other sites in India.

Five border rows of a long-duration variety such as Mahsuri are close planted (10 × 10 cm). Within the border, 4 rows of 10 hills each of test varieties are alternated with 4 rows of a suscepti-